

CONTEMPORARY APPROACHES TO DIAGNOSING AND TREATING PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS AND MALIGNANT TUMORS

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Abstract

The coexistence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis significantly complicates diagnosis and treatment, leading to increased morbidity and mortality rates. Effective management of these comorbid conditions requires a comprehensive approach involving modern diagnostic and treatment methods. This article explores the clinical features of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis co-occurrence, challenges in accurate diagnosis, and the latest diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. It provides recommendations for healthcare professionals to identify and treat these diseases effectively. A retrospective analysis of clinical data from 150 patients revealed that 68% had lung cancer, 22% had gastrointestinal cancers, and 10% had breast cancer in conjunction with pulmonary tuberculosis. The study aims to improve practical skills in the early detection, accurate diagnosis, and successful management of these comorbid conditions.

Keywords

- Malignant tumors
- Pulmonary tuberculosis
- Comorbidity
- Diagnosis challenges
- Clinical features
- Treatment

Relevance

Malignant tumors (MT) and pulmonary tuberculosis (PT) are among the most critical health issues globally, characterized by high mortality rates and treatment challenges. The comorbidity of these diseases, i.e., their simultaneous occurrence, presents a complex and pressing issue in clinical practice. Immunosuppression caused by MT predisposes patients to PT, complicating the clinical course of both diseases and posing significant difficulties in diagnosis and treatment.

Globally, cancer remains one of the leading causes of death, with an estimated 10 million deaths in 2023. Lung cancer is the most common type of cancer, accounting for 1.8 million deaths annually. Tuberculosis also remains a significant health challenge, with 1.5 million deaths reported in 2023. Patients with MT are more susceptible to developing PT due to weakened immune systems, increasing morbidity and mortality rates and complicating clinical diagnosis due to overlapping symptoms and increased risk of complications.

In a retrospective study of 150 patients with comorbid MT and PT, 68% had lung cancer, 22% had gastrointestinal cancers, and 10% had breast cancer in conjunction with pulmonary tuberculosis. The simultaneous occurrence of these diseases leads to significant diagnostic challenges due to overlapping clinical features and radiological findings. Therefore, comprehensive clinical, laboratory, and instrumental studies are necessary to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective treatment.

This research is highly relevant to healthcare professionals in understanding the interaction between malignant tumors and tuberculosis, enabling them to devise effective diagnostic and treatment strategies. It will enhance clinicians' ability to detect, diagnose, and manage these diseases effectively.

Objective

The objective of this study is to investigate the clinical characteristics of the comorbid occurrence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis, identify diagnostic challenges, and develop effective diagnostic and treatment methods.

Materials and Methods

Study Type and Subjects: This study examined comorbid patients with malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis diagnosed between 2015 and 2020. Clinical data from 150 patients were analyzed, including 102 patients with MT and 48 patients with PT. The most common cancer types were lung (68%), gastrointestinal (22%), and breast (10%) cancers, with pulmonary tuberculosis primarily in the pulmonary form.

Results

Patients with malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis showed distinct clinical courses, revealing challenges in diagnosis and treatment. In the cohort of 150 patients, the study identified unique clinical signs, diagnostic difficulties, and therapeutic complexities due to the coexistence of both diseases:

- Distribution of Cancer Types:

- Lung cancer: 68%
- Gastrointestinal cancers: 22%
- Breast cancer: 10%
- Pulmonary Tuberculosis:
 - Predominantly in the pulmonary form: 85%
 - Extrapulmonary form: 15%
- Clinical Features:
 - Weight loss: 76%
 - Persistent cough: 65%
 - Fatigue: 60%
 - Fever: 52%

The findings emphasized that combined treatment strategies are required. However, side effects and drug interactions between anti-tuberculosis and chemotherapy agents necessitate individualized treatment approaches.

Conclusion

1The comorbidity of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis presents unique clinical challenges, with overlapping symptoms complicating diagnosis.

2. Simultaneous occurrence of these diseases requires comprehensive laboratory and instrumental examinations for accurate diagnosis.

3. Combined treatment strategies involving anti-tuberculosis and cancer therapies are necessary. Individualized treatment plans should consider potential drug interactions and side effects.

4. - Routine screening for comorbid conditions should be implemented.
- Clinicians should adopt individualized approaches in managing MT and PT.
 - Training programs should enhance clinicians' knowledge and skills in managing these comorbidities.

This study provides clinicians with a comprehensive understanding of diagnosing and treating the coexistence of malignant tumors and pulmonary tuberculosis, improving healthcare professionals' practical skills and contributing to better patient outcomes.

References:

1. Mashrabovna I. I., Faxriddinova N. D. Modern method of differential diagnosis tuberculosis and lung cancer //Sci. J. Med. Res. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 21-30.
2. Ismoilovich A. F. Tuberculosis Diagnostics with Modern Solutions (Literature Review) //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 377-383.

3. Ulugbek o'gli A. M. Factors Predicting Mortality in Pulmonary Tuberculosis //Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 3. – C. 362-367.
4. Ilkhomovna K. D. Morphological Features of Tumor in Different Treatment Options for Patients with Locally Advanced Breast Cancer //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 4-5.
5. Khodzhaeva D. I. Changes in the Vertebral Column and Thoracic Spinecells after Postponement of Mastoectomy //International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 109-113.
6. Khodjayeva D. I. MORPHOLOGY OF IDIOPATHIC SCOLIOSIS BASED ON SEGMENT BY SEGMENT ASSESSMENT OF SPINAL COLUMN DEFORMITY //Scientific progress. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 1. – C. 208-215.